

PROCESSING AND TACTICITY EFFECT ON GLASS TRANSITION TEMPERATURE OF PMMA/GRAPHENE NANO-COMPOSITES.

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1 Introduction

Graphene has recently attracted wide interest because of its 2-D structure and outstanding electrical and mechanical properties. Due to its high surface area and aspect ratio, graphene is capable to improve mechanical properties, gas impermeability and electrical conductivities of polymer [1, 2]. However, it is not clear whether the glass transition temperature (T_g) changes with incorporation of graphene in polymers.

In this work, PMMA/graphene nano-composites were prepared by *in situ* polymerization and solvent blending. The effect of these two processing methods and also tacticity on T_g was investigated and related to interface interaction between PMMA and graphene.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

The atactic PMMA (a-PMMA; Polysciences, Mw = 350,000, PDI = 2.7), isotactic PMMA (i-PMMA; Sigma Aldrich, 97% isotactic), methyl-methacrylate monomer (MMA; Aldrich, 99%), tetrahydrofuran (THF), methanol, 2,2'-azobis(2-methylpropionitrile (AIBN), thermally reduced graphene sheets (TRG; Vorbeck Materials, C/O=9/1) and near pristine graphene (PG; N002-PDR, Angstrom Materials C/O=49/1) were used in this work.

2.2 Preparation of samples

PMMA/graphene/THF suspensions with different loading of graphene (0-1wt% in PMMA) were precipitated in methanol and collected by filtration, and then dried at 80 °C under vacuum for 10 h respectively. *In situ* polymerization of MMA /

graphene/THF suspensions with different loading of graphene (0-1wt% in PMMA) were carried out at 65 °C for 24 h under N₂ (initiator: AIBN). After polymerization, the obtained polymerized samples were dried in a hood at 80 °C for 24 h under N₂. Samples were dried at 120 °C in vacuum for 24 h, and then the sheet samples were formed by pressing at 210 °C at 2 MPa for 5 min.

PMMA thin films and graphene papers for contact angle measurement were also prepared by spin coating on glass substrate, by filtration from graphene/ THF suspensions, respectively.

2.3 Characterization

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) measurements were performed using a TA Instruments Q1000 at a rate of 10 °C/min. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) were measured by Nicolet Macna - IR760 Spectrometer for graphene, and by Bruker ALPHA FT-IR Spectrometer for nano-composites sheets. Contact angle measurements of water on graphene paper and PMMA were performed using a Kyowa Interface Science Microscopic Contact Angle meter MCA-3. Raman spectra were measured by WITec An alpha 300R confocal Raman microscope. An air-cooled argon-ion laser operating at wavelength of 514.5 nm was used as an excitation source.

3 Results and discussion

T_g of PMMA/graphene nano-composites by DSC are shown in Fig.1. T_g changes are different with processing and tacticity. *In situ* polymerized PMMA /TRG nano-composites showed the biggest increase of T_g . Among the solvent blended samples, only T_g of i-PMMA based nano-composites were increased.

Fig 1. T_g of PMMA/graphene nano-composites

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) of TRG and extracted TRG are shown in Fig 2.

Fig 2. Fourier transform infrared spectra from TRG and extracted TRG. The spectra were recorded in transmission mode.

Compared to the spectrum from TRG, the spectrum from extracted TRG has O-CH₃ peak (2700-3000cm⁻¹), C=O peak (1727 cm⁻¹) and OCH₂-H peak and α-CH₂-H (1430-1480 cm⁻¹) [3, 4]. Presence of these peaks clearly suggests that PMMA exists on graphene surface.

Contact angle measurements were conducted for estimation of affinity between PMMA and graphene. Contact angle of water on graphene paper and PMMA are shown Table 2. Here, extracted TRG was the TRG removed by filtration from *in situ* polymerized PMMA/TRG nano-composites.

Table 2. Contact angles of water

PG	130.7	a-PMMA	68.4
TRG	110.2	i-PMMA	69.6
Extracted TRG	104.0	<i>in situ</i> PMMA	69.7

Contact angle of extracted TRG became smaller than that of ordinary TRG, and closer to that of PMMA. This suggests that the affinity between PMMA and graphene is increased by PMMA chains covalently bonded on the surface of graphene during *in situ* polymerization. Torkelson *et al.* reported that a well wetted matrix polymer/filler interface can lead to a stronger interaction to increase T_g [5]. The bonded PMMA chains on TRG enhanced wetting during *in situ* polymerization and cause the large T_g increase.

FT-IR spectra of solvent blended PMMA/TRG nano-composites are shown in Fig 3.

Fig 3. FT-IR spectra in carbonyl area of TRG/PMMA nano-composites. (Intensity of peaks are normalized at 1723cm⁻¹).

The peak changes at lower frequency of i-PMMA/TRG nano-composites indicate hydrogen bonding with graphene.

Raman spectra of solvent blended PMMA/graphene nano-composites were also measured for evaluation of for the conformation of PMMA. The changes of peak ratio of C-H₂ stretching (2953cm⁻¹, I₂₉₅₃), and C-C, C=O side chain stretching(812cm⁻¹, I₈₁₂), I₂₉₅₃/I₈₁₂, of PMMA were shown in Fig 4.

Fig 4. The changes of the peak ratio I_{2953}/I_{812} of solvent blended PMMA/graphene nano-composites

The peak ratio, I_{2953}/I_{812} , of a-PMMA/TRG nano-composites stays almost constant, while the peak ratio of both i-PMMA/TRG and i-PMMA/PG nano-composites increase with an increase of concentration of graphene.

Grohens *et al* reported that the degree of peak shift of carbonyl area of PMMA in FT-IR spectrum is related with the number of surface-bonded carbonyl group of PMMA thin films on silica and alumina substrates, and they found that T_g of i-PMMA thin films increased more than T_g of a-PMMA due to the higher number of hydrogen bond between PMMA and the substrates [6]. Chen *et al.* reported that the peak ratio of change, I_{2953}/I_{812} , of PMMA in Raman spectrum is related with the orientation of PMMA chains at interface between PMMA and SWCNT. A higher value of I_{2953}/I_{812} represents stronger anisotropy interaction between PMMA and SWCNT [7]. Referring to the study by Grohens *et al.* and Chen *et al.*, the results suggest that the main chains of i-PMMA at the interface are aligned by graphene sheets. The aligned PMMA chains have higher interaction with graphene, and were confined stronger than a-PMMA in solvent blended nano-composites. This may cause larger T_g increase of i-PMMA/graphene nano-composites compared with a-PMMA/graphene nano-composites.

4. Conclusion

T_g of PMMA/graphene nano-composites are affected by processing and tacticity. *In situ* polymerization causes a significant increase, $\sim 9^\circ\text{C}$, of T_g , whereas solvent blending of a-PMMA showed no increase. PMMA appears to covalently bond to

TRG during polymerization. Tacticity of PMMA does affect T_g of solvent blended nano-composites. i-PMMA chains can interact with graphene with higher interaction density and are confined more strongly than a-PMMA in nano-composites. This stronger interaction causes $\sim 2^\circ\text{C}$ T_g increase of i-PMMA based nano-composites.

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